

Assessing the Suitability of Photogrammetric 3D Reconstruction by Open-Source Pipeline for Tunnel Condition Monitoring

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Summary

This study explores the use of open-source photogrammetric software, particularly Meshroom, for 3D reconstruction in tunnel inspection. Despite challenges like low-light conditions and dust, Meshroom successfully reconstructed tunnel segments with a residual error of RMSE 0.9. The study demonstrates the software's viability for inspection purposes, offering cost-effective solutions without compromising quality. However, limitations such as laptop capacity constraints were encountered.

Overall, the research underscores the potential of open-source software in civil engineering, facilitating efficient and accurate data processing in traditionally labor-intensive tasks, thereby contributing to the ongoing digitalization of the construction industry.

KEYWORDS: 3D reconstruction, AliceVision Meshroom, Structure from Motion, Reprojection error, Bundle Adjustment.

1 Introduction

This study concentrates on investigating 3D reconstruction using open-source photogrammetric software for a tunnel dataset. Meshroom, a free open-source 3D reconstruction software is used for processing the data.

The dataset used for the assessment is taken from (Panella et al., 2020) which provides the findings and outcomes from Arup's proposed research project, in collaboration with Network Rail High-Speed Ltd. (NRHS).

1.1 Specific Aims

- To check whether the results from an open-source 3D reconstruction software (Meshroom) provide the required accuracy for the tunnel inspection.
- Compare results with commercial software (Agisoft Metashape)
- Compare Meshroom results with different datasets from previous papers.

2 Experiment

2.1 Data Used

The data captured is of a 50m section of a 7.15m diameter, concrete segmentally lined tunnel (HS1, London), used for high-speed rail traffic. A camera system consisting of 9 GoPro cameras mounted on an aluminum frame was used for data capture. The data was captured by 9 cameras simultaneously, along with a lighting system consisting of 6 LED lights (5k lumen each) radially fitted on the aluminum frame to increase camera resolution (**Figure 1**). The setup cost £3.5k at the time of capture. GoPro

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Hero3+ cameras (**Figure 2**) were chosen after a laboratory test for checking the resolving power of lenses using the 1951 Usaf Resolution Chart. The camera specifications are as shown in **Table 1**. A total of 414 photos (from 9 cameras at 46 stops) were used as input data for the reconstruction.

Figure 1 Test setup (Panella et al., 2020)

Figure 2 GoPro Hero3+ (“GoPro Official Website - Capture + share your world - HERO3+,” n.d.)

Table 1 Camera Specifications

Camera Specifications (GoPro)	
Type	Fisheye
Resolution	(4000px) x (3000px)
Focal Length	2.77 m
Pixel Size	1.6 μ m x 1.6 μ m

2.2 Data Processing

Meshroom was selected for its user-friendliness and popularity. Its clear nodal system displays each step in the photogrammetry process, with adjustable parameters. The default pipeline simplifies 3D reconstruction for all users, requiring minimal hardware (Lanthyony, 2021).

The setup used for this study is outlined in **Table 2**.

Table 2 Setup Used for this study

Software Version	Meshroom 2019.2.0
OS	Windows 10
Graphics Card	NVIDIA GeForce MX130
Compute capability	6.1

The default photogrammetry pipeline employed by Meshroom is illustrated in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3 Complete Default Pipeline of Photogrammetry in Meshroom

① Camera Initialization

When the images to be used for 3D reconstruction are uploaded into the software, the system extracts camera metadata, and camera intrinsics are stored in the system. Number of views of the camera is listed and the default field of view is set at 45°. Camera metadata displayed in Meshroom for a viewpoint is depicted in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4 Camera metadata shown in Meshroom for a viewpoint

② Natural Feature Extraction

Distinctive groups of pixels invariant to different viewpoints are extracted using SIFT (Scale Invariant Feature Transform) (Lowe, 1999) (**Figure 5**). A post-filtering step controls the number of extracted features. **Figure 5** shows that 5835 feature points were extracted from the respective image.

Figure 5 Feature Extraction done by SIFT algorithm

③ Image Matching

Images looking at the same areas of a scene are matched using a vocabulary tree approach and a list of image pairs is obtained which is given as a text file by Meshroom.

④ Features Matching

Feature matching between image pairs utilizes the Approximate Nearest Neighbor (ANN) algorithm (Muja and Lowe, 2009), followed by geometric filtering using epipolar geometry to ensure adherence to scene constraints.

⑤ Structure from Motion (SfM)

Rigid scene structure with 3D points is obtained in this process. The default pipeline uses Incremental Bundle Adjustment (IBA) for refining the positions of 3D points and the cameras, minimizing errors. The results are then filtered by removing the observations with high reprojection errors and insufficient angles between observations.

Figure 6 illustrates the obtained sparse point cloud.

Figure 6 Sparse point cloud obtained

The whole 'Structure from Motion' task took approximately 13 minutes.

The process was halted after obtaining a sparse point cloud, as the quality of the final dense reconstruction depends directly on the image orientation from SfM (Stathopoulou et al., 2019).

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Summary

A sparse point cloud was obtained containing a total of 263,514 3D points. The Structure from Motion node took 790.48 seconds to compute and generate the sparse point cloud. Reprojection error and no of oriented cameras were chosen for checking the output quality.

Reprojection error - A residual RMSE of 0.82px was obtained with IBA (Incremental Bundle Adjustment).
 - A residual RMSE of 0.69 px was obtained with GBA (Global Bundle Adjustment).

No. of cameras oriented – 414, i.e., all the input images were oriented.

Meshroom exhibits an RMS reprojection error of 0.82 pixels with IBA and 0.69 pixels with GBA, both exceeding Agisoft Metashape's 0.19 pixels for the same dataset. However, an RMSE < 1 pixel, a standard for close-range engineering monitoring (Habib et al., 2008), is achieved.

3.2 Analysis

A two-tier comparison study is done.

1) With the results obtained in Agisoft Metashape of the same data by (Panella et al., 2020), shown in **Table 3**.

Table 3 Comparison with Agisoft Metashape

	AliceVisionMeshroom		(Panella et al., 2020) – Agisoft Metashape
	IBA	GBA	
Total number of input images	414	414	414
Reprojection error (RMSE)(pixels)	0.82	0.69	0.19
No. of oriented images	414	414	414

Here, RMSE with both IBA and GBA is less than 1 pixel, which is the standard threshold. Meshroom has also oriented all the images.

2) With the results obtained by (Stathopoulou et al., 2019) in AliceVision Meshroom for a variety of datasets, captured in open-environment, featuring various number of images, acquisition platforms and sensor sizes, shown in **Table 4**.

Table 4 Comparison Summary with data captured in open-environment.

Dataset description	Type	Camera	No. of Images	Image resolution & size(px)	RMSE Reprojection error(px)	
					IBA	GBA
Nettuno Aerial (Ancient Temple)	Aerial/UAV	Canon EOS 550D, 22.3 x 14.9 mm CMOS sensor, 25mm focal	212	18 MPx, 5184*3456 px (scaled to 1/2)	0.91	0.95
Nettuno Terrestrial (Ancient Temple)	Terrestrial	Nikon D3X, 36x24 mm CMOS sensor, 50mm focal length	404	24 MPx, 6048*4032 px (scaled to 1/2)	0.53	0.57
Nettuno Fused	Aerial + Terrestrial	as in Nettuno_aer & Nettuno_terr	616	as in Nettuno_aer & Nettuno_terr	0.74	0.88
Barn Tat	Terrestrial	Sony A7SM2, 23.9 x 35.8 mm CMOS sensor, 21 mm focal length	410	2.1 MPx, 1920*1080 px	0.7	0.52
Modena (Church gate)	Terrestrial	Nikon D750, 35.9 x 24 mm CMOS sensor, 28 mm focal length	55	24 Mpx, 6016*4016 px	0.82	0.9
3DOMcity	Aerial (nadir+oblique)	Nikon D750, 35.9 x 24 mm CMOS sensor, 50 mm focal length	420	24 Mpx, 6016*4016px	0.54	0.41
HS1 tunnel	Terrestrial (under tunnel environment)	GoPro Hero3+, CMOS sensor, 2.77 mm focal length	414	5 MPx, 4000*3000px	0.82	0.69

Table 4 illustrates that despite the use of low-end sensor data, better performance in terms of RMS reprojection error was achieved. Results vary widely even with cameras of similar specifications, indicating the dependence on image overlap rather than camera quality.

4 Conclusions

Meshroom provided comparable results with a complete orientation of the images and an RMS reprojection error of 0.69 px using GBA. This is a commendable output considering the following factors –

- 1) Data captured using low-end sensors
- 2) Low cost of the test-setup (3.1 k £)
- 3) Challenging environment of tunnel including lack of light, presence of dust and difficulty in capturing the dataset.
- 4) Free, user-friendly and continually evolving open-source pipeline used for the reconstruction, reducing the cost factor.

This study elucidates the capability of open-source image-based software for 3D reconstruction and thus it demands further research on the same.

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Biographies

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